

Regional Impact Analysis of Large-scale Research Infrastructures

ADDENDUM FCC-GOV-CC-0185 (KE4819/ATS)

Case study selection and methodology

(LSE-RD-1.4-1.5/Doc)

Riccardo Crescenzi and Gabriele Piazza

London School of Economics

V 0.1, 28 December 2022, edited by R. Crescenzi and G. Piazza (LSE)

V 0.2, 29 December 2022, reviewed by J. Gutleber (CERN)

V 0.3, 16 January 2023, edited by R. Crescenzi and G. Piazza (LSE)

V 1.0 (released), 19 January 2023, approved by J. Gutleber (CERN)

The FCCIS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant No 951754.

The London School of Economics (LSE) has received funding from European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) under Addendum FCC-GOV-CC-0185 (KE4819/ATS), defining LSE contribution under Article 6 of the Memorandum of Understanding for the Future Circular Collider Innovation Study (FCCIS) (FCC-GOV-CC-0004, EDMS 1390795) hosted by CERN.

Contents

List of Abbreviations.....	4
Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Motivation.....	7
1.2 Existing evidence and gaps.....	7
1.3 Aims of this study	8
1.4 Structure of the report	9
2. Case study.....	10
2.1 Superconducting radiofrequency cavities.....	10
2.2 The European XFEL project.....	13
2.3 The procurement and manufacturing process for the European XFEL.....	14
2.4 E. Zanon and Schio: the selection of the regional case study	17
3. Approach.....	24
3.1 Conceptual framework	24
3.11 Employment effects on the supplier’s industry beyond the boundaries of the firm	25
3.12 Employment effects on linked sectors	26
3.13 Employment effects on local consumption.....	27
3.2 Methodology.....	27
3.3 Data.....	29
4. Results	31
4.1 Impact on municipalities	31
4.11 Manufacturing	34
4.12 Linked sectors.....	40
4.13 Consumption	40
4.2 Impact on Labour Market Areas.....	41
4.21 Manufacturing	45
4.22 Linked sectors.....	47
4.23 Consumption	49
4.3 Robustness checks	50
4.4 Displacement.....	50
4.5 Comparison to other estimates in the literature.....	51
5. Conclusions	53
Appendix A: List of interviewees	55
Appendix B: Data preparation steps	56
Appendix C: Impact on selected individual sectors.....	57

List of References58

List of Abbreviations

CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
DESY	German Electron Synchrotron
FCC	Future Circular Collider
HEP	High-energy Physics
INFN	National Institute for Nuclear Physics
ISTAT	Italian National Statistical Office
ITER	International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LMA	Labour Market Area
PPI	Public Procurement for Innovation
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCM	Synthetic Control Method
SRF	Superconducting Radiofrequency
TBM	Trajectory Balancing Method
XFEL	European X-Ray Free-Electron Laser Facility

Executive summary

This report has been prepared as part of the regional impact of large-scale research infrastructures (RIs) study agreed between the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) (deliverables LSE-RD 1.4 and 1.5).

This document outlines a novel framework to identify and estimate the regional economic impacts that a new particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a globally distributed project can create through their procurement. To test the validity of this new approach and estimate the potential regional and local economic impacts of RI procurement, this report examines the effects of a technology of relevance for the Future Circular Collider (FCC): superconducting radiofrequency cavities (SRF). To evaluate the regional impacts of this technology, this study uses the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) facility in Germany as a case study. This project involved the largest deployment of superconducting radiofrequency cavity technology to date. Schio, a municipality in Italy where one of the two suppliers for this procurement contract is located, is the focus of the analysis. By studying the local economic impact of SRF procurement by XFEL, this report can estimate real world (i.e. non-simulated) counterfactual (i.e. over and above what would have happened in the local economy without such SRF procurement contract) effects, offering insights on the regional and local impacts of future FCC high-tech industry procurement for this and other, comparable technologies.

This study provides new evidence on the positive local impact of RI procurement. This report finds that the high-tech procurement contracts for a large-scale scientific project positively affected manufacturing employment in the supplier's municipality well beyond the boundaries of the procurement contract with effects beyond the firm that received the contract. Every new employee that the supplier added to its internal workforce to fulfil the contract supported 15 additional manufacturing jobs outside the firm's boundaries. In monetary terms, each one million euros spent on procurement supported additional 11 manufacturing jobs in the supplier's municipality. As a result of this contract, the number of manufacturing employees in Schio was 7% higher than it would have been in the absence of SRF procurement.

The results of this report suggest that **the positive employment effect remained concentrated within the industrial manufacturing sector. The effect was geographically concentrated** within the municipality of Schio.

This report focuses on a large high-technology-intensive contract. **The advantage of the proposed approach to the estimation of the local impacts of RI procurement is that it**

can be applied to other technology procurement cases to better understand the heterogeneity of such effects. For example, it can be used to understand how different technologies, different contract volumes and different technology intensity would impact the local economy in which the supplier is located in different ways.

The results indicate that the employment effect on the local economy of RI procurement contracts is significant, can be large and should be considered when making investment decisions for an FCC project.

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Large Research Infrastructures (RIs) are crucial for advancing science for two reasons. Firstly, science evolves rapidly and to push forward the frontiers of scientific knowledge, scientists need new experimental instruments (Bloom 2020). Secondly, new scientific discoveries are increasingly becoming the result of collaborative efforts (Crescenzi et al., 2016). RIs involve a wide range of actors, such as universities and other research centres, receive funds from national governments and work with several industrial partners to develop new cutting-edge technologies needed to fulfil their ambitious research objectives (Bastianin et al., 2021). Because of all these features, RIs can play an important role in creating innovation systems.

Understanding the socio-economic impact of an RI at different levels (local, regional, national, and global) is crucial for both RIs managers and policymakers. Governments want answers to the following questions: given finite annual budgets, which RIs should a government fund over long periods? Are there benefits for society from supporting these projects that go beyond the long-term scientific gains? If positive effects can be identified, how widespread are they, and who benefits from them?

While it is important to identify the socio-economic returns of these scientific endeavours, incorporating socio-economic aspects into RI planning and design poses some critical challenges and questions for the scientific community. For example, to what extent and how can an infrastructure pursue societally beneficial goals that are separate from its main scientific missions without negatively affecting these?

1.2 Existing evidence and gaps

Most of the literature has focused on the direct effects of procurement, and this is because the quest for new discoveries needs ever more complex components. Consequently, technology-intensive equipment takes an increasingly higher share of the budget for these scientific projects. The significant funds involved, the technology intensity of these contracts and the required collaboration between industry and scientists to design and develop these products have made procurement a likely and identifiable channel through which RIs can generate wider economic benefits. At the same time, procurement has become an important tool for innovation policy - public procurement for innovation (PPI) - having the potential to support the development of novel technologies that are too risky for the private sector to invest in (Uyarra et al. 2014).

Much of the recent evidence on the socio-economic benefits of RI procurement comes from CERN, which hosts the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), one of the largest RIs ever built (Florio,

2019). Looking at LHC suppliers, Castelnovo et al. (2018) demonstrated that companies generally experienced a rise in R&D, patents, productivity, and profits after becoming CERN industrial partners. Florio et al. (2018) showed that CERN procurement significantly affects suppliers' innovative performance when a relational type of governance is in place through cooperative relations (i.e. exchanges implying that CERN and suppliers work closely to deal with complex information that is not easily transmitted or learned). Bastianin et al. (2021) showed that collaborating with CERN is associated with an increase in the probability of filing a patent for the first time and in the number of patent applications. Studies also found that spillovers to second-tier suppliers impact the entire supply chain (Florio et al., 2018). However, **most of the latest socio-economic studies measure the effects on the direct beneficiaries of procurement contracts. The benefits are likely to go beyond the boundaries of individual firms and affect the entire local economy in which these firms are located and operate** (Crescenzi and Piazza, 2023). But we still have no clear evidence on whether this is the case, the size of these potential effects and how widely they spread.

1.3 Aims of this study

Against this background, **this study develops a new framework to identify and estimate the regional effects that a particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a worldwide distributed project can generate** by focusing on the procurement channel. More specifically, this study focuses on a particular type of regional and local impacts of RIs involved in High-Energy Physics (HEP).

We build on Moretti's (2010) local multiplier and hypothesize that **large RI procurement contracts can boost demand in the supplier's industry and linked sectors**. In addition, **these procurement activities need a qualified workforce, and their earnings can boost local consumption and employment in local services**.

This framework allows us to move beyond the measurement of innovative outcomes and estimate the local multiplicative effects of this type of procurement contract in terms of short- and medium-term employment. To estimate these effects, **we use the Trajectory Balancing Method developed by Hazlett and Xu (2018) to build "synthetic" counterfactuals**. The main advantage of this approach is that it can be applied to other case studies involving different types of RIs, contracts, firms and regions to understand the role of these mediating factors. This approach aims to contribute to the existing body of evidence on the effects of HEP procurement that has primarily focused on supplying firms. **The idea behind the approach is that the benefits to the supplier and the wider local economy can be integrated into a single framework**.

To test our approach, we decided to focus on one technology that is particularly relevant for the Future Circular Collider project: superconducting radiofrequency (SRF) cavities. We chose this technology for two reasons. Firstly, SRF systems will be at the heart of the FCC-ee (Benedikt, 2020). Secondly, the fact that SRF cavities are exclusively produced for particle accelerators makes it easier to attribute the impact that we observe to the procurement contract. **To test the local impact of this technology, we focus on the procurement actions carried out for the construction of the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) facility in Germany (Denis et al. 2019).** This linear particle accelerator involved the largest deployment of this technology to date. Two firms, E. Zanon (today Zanon Research & Innovation) and Research Instruments GmbH, located in two different countries, Italy and Germany, were involved in the XFEL production. **In this study, we focus on E. Zanon and the municipality of Schio (Italy), where the company is located.** Two factors have determined this choice. Firstly, the physic branch of E. Zanon has only one site. Secondly, the entire staff was involved in fulfilling the contract. This makes it easier to attribute the effect we might observe to the procurement contract and an ideal setting to test our methodology.

1.4 Structure of the report

The rest of report is structured as follows: Section 2 describes our case study. In particular, it reports the insights from the expert interviews we conducted with firms and research institutes and justifies the case study selection. Section 3 outlines our approach to identify and estimate the impacts of the contracts. Section 4 presents and discusses the results. Section 5 concludes by highlighting the implications of this study's results.

2. Case study

This section outlines the rationale for choosing the Schio area in Italy for the analysis, where E. Zanon, one of the two companies that produced SRF cavities for the XFEL project, is located. The choice was informed by a detailed analysis of related conference proceedings and expert interviews conducted between December 2020 and September 2022. The “pyramiding” sampling procedure was used to build our sample of experts. This is a sampling method in which one interviewee provides the researcher with the name of one or more potential interviewees who are more expert than themselves (Noy, 2008). Appendix A provides the complete list of interviewees.

Then, this section outlines the criteria for choosing SRF cavities as the technology for the case study. It describes the XFEL project, specifically the procurement and production process for the SRF cavities. Finally, it explains the reasons for selecting E. Zanon and, consequently, the Schio area for the analysis.

2.1 Superconducting radiofrequency cavities

To estimate the regional effects that a particle-collider-based research infrastructure set up as a worldwide collaborative project can create, together with CERN, we have decided to focus on one technology, SRF cavities. Box 1 provides more details about the technology and its market.

This technology met the following four criteria. Firstly, it is a technology that will be important for the FCC. As a first stage, the proposed FCC programme features an electron-positron Higgs and electroweak factory (FCC-ee). SRF cavities will be at the heart of the FCC-ee: over 11 years, 341 cryomodules (containing 1364 cavities) will be produced (Benedikt, 2020). This would be the largest deployment of this technology to date.

Secondly, the selected technology should only be used in HEP so that we can attribute the effects we observe to the procurement contract. The interviews confirmed that SRF cavities are only used for particle accelerators. This does not exclude significant socio-economic impacts along the SRF value chain. For instance, advanced thin-film coating and forming methods for 3D complicated geometries have already been shown to be relevant for numerous consumer product areas including for instance the coating of the iPhone.¹

Thirdly, the production of this technology needed close collaboration between RIs and firms. The evidence shows that this type of relationship is conducive to knowledge flows (Florio et al., 2018). This increases the possibility of knowledge spillovers that might benefit

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/High-power_impulse_magnetron_sputtering

economic agents located in the supplier's area. Interviews with firms and RIs involved in the production of SRF cavities revealed that this type of collaboration was in place for most SRF cavities projects, particularly for the European XFEL project.

Fourthly, we wanted to select a technology that, beyond the primary element produced for a particle collider (the superconducting cavities), has potential for use outside HEP.

This would increase the possibility of affecting the local economy. At the same time, to identify the effect of the contract, we wanted to focus on a technology that has not yet had an application outside the research domain. Although SRF cavities are only used in particle accelerators, a recent study by Quach et al., (2021) showed that High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering, a coating technology that is being considered for the production of SRF cavities for FCC-ee to reduce its costs and increase quality, is already employed in some areas of automotive (e.g. reflectors), medical (e.g. implants) and communication industries (e.g. the coating of the Apple iPhone screen). CERN investment and demand could trigger new developments for this coating technology (Quach et al., 2021). Qualified personnel who can master this technology reliably are scarce and much sought after. It is important to stress that other regional evaluations could have different criteria for selecting the technology and put less emphasis on the criteria listed here.

Box 1: SRF cavities market

The heart of a superconducting particle acceleration structure is a hollow structure called cavity, made of a superconducting material (or copper, coated with a superconducting material), in most cases niobium, chilled to near absolute zero with liquid helium. The generator fills the cavity with a radio-frequency electric field to accelerate the charged particles. These superconducting cavities conduct electric current with very small loss of energy so that a large amount of the energy coming from the electrical supply can be almost entirely transferred to the beam. The design of SRF varies depending on the particle types and energy requirements. Multiple SRF cavities are incorporated into linear assemblies known as cryomodules.

Superconducting radiofrequency systems technology has existed for 50 years (Peiniger et al., 2012). The first 20 years involved R&D and prototyping at research centres and universities. Industry has now been involved for 30 years in the production of cavities and accelerator modules with quality improvements over this period (Peiniger et al., 2012). The production of SRF cavities requires advanced milling and turning machines, metal forming, electron beam welding, and chemical treatment facilities (Peiniger et al., 2012), advanced thin-film production processes (e.g. magnetron sputtering) as well as novel forming processes such as electro-hydraulic forming. When the production of SRF cavities in the industry started, some machines could be found in companies involved in the manufacture of nuclear power plants. For companies not already having this equipment, a significant investment is required. The demand for SRF technologies has been stable through the last three decades and an average 100 cavities per year have been produced since the mid-1980s. However, interviews with the two companies revealed that demand fluctuates considerably. Research Instrument GmbH in Germany is the largest market player, producing on average 70 cavities per year since 2010. E. Zanon (now Zanon Research & Innovation) is the other company able to produce SRF cavities. The average value of one cavity built from bulk niobium is estimated at 100'000 euros in 2020 and this would suggest that the turnover for SRF cavity production is about 10 million euros (Peiniger et al., 2012). This is low if we take into consideration the initial investment to produce the cavities and it might explain the low number of firms involved in the production of SRF technology and why companies involved try to diversify. However, the cavity is only one small part of the SRF system and the turnover for the entire production is considerably higher.

In the last decade, the SRF market has been dominated by the construction of the European XFEL (840 cavities), the FRIB project at MSU (340 cavities) the ESS project at Lund (240 cavities) and SLAC (210 cavities) (Peiniger et al., 2012; Weise, 2014). Before XFEL, only the fabrication was done by industry with the final treatment being done by the commissioning research institutes (Peiniger et al., 2012). XFEL is the largest deployment of this technology project to date and included many partner laboratories and technology transfer to industry for mass production. If the ILC and the FCC-ee are built, the production of SRF cavities is set to increase in the coming years.

2.2 The European XFEL project

One of the challenges in measuring the potential regional impact of SRF cavities is that it has not been used at CERN in the scales and level of industry involvement needed for the FCC-ee. This means that one cannot use recent CERN procurement data and related evidence to estimate the impact of this technology.

To address this challenge, we have examined past completed projects that have developed SRF systems with industry on a large scale. After having conducted interviews with staff at various research organizations (Jefferson Lab (United States), DESY (Germany), CERN (Switzerland), INFN (Italy)) and companies (Research Instruments (Germany), Zanon Research & Innovation (Italy), AES (USA), Roark (USA)), **we have identified the European X-ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) in Germany as the primary case study for this analysis.** Box 2 below provides more details on this project.

We have selected this case for two reasons. Firstly, this was the first project in which SRF cavities were mainly produced by industry. Before this production, only the mechanical fabrication was done by companies, while the surface treatment, the most demanding part of the production, was done by the commissioning research institutes (Singer et al., 2016). **Secondly, this was the largest deployment of SRF cavities to date** (Singer et al., 2016). And the underlying TESLA technology (Kako et al., 2020) for these cavities has become a standard for other accelerators.

It is important to note that the methodological approach we outline in the next section could also be applied to other scientific projects that have adopted this technology in different quantities and qualities and various levels of industry involvement.

Box 2: Building the European XFEL

The European X-ray free-Electronic Laser is a research facility located in the Hamburg area, Germany, where scientists from all over the world carry out experiments using X-ray flashes. The almost 2.1-km-long superconducting linear accelerator of XFEL will accelerate electrons to a maximum energy of 17.5 GeV by using a total of 808 SRF cavities installed in the three main linac sections.

To construct and operate the European XFEL, international partners created an independent research organisation – the European XFEL GmbH, a non-profit limited liability company under German law. The company employs more than 300 people. Twelve countries participated in this project: Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK. Its construction was a joint effort of its partners. It started in early 2009, with the first experiments beginning in September 2017. The costs amount to 1.25 billion euro (in 2005 prices). Germany covered 57% of these costs, Russia 26% and international partners the rest. Most of the contributions were in-kind.

2.3 The procurement and manufacturing process for the European XFEL

Before discussing the criteria for the municipality selection, it is helpful to outline the specificities of the procurement and production process of the SRF cavities for XFEL, as these might influence the magnitude of the territorial impact.

After a period of pre-qualification during which at least three companies were surveyed, the order for 840 cavities was placed in 2010. The production started in 2012 and ended in 2015. The first of the series of cavities was delivered at the beginning of 2013. The National Centre Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) in Germany managed and assigned the contracts to two companies: Research Instruments GmbH in Bergisch Gladbach and Dortmund (Germany) and E. Zanon in Schio (Italy). E. Zanon and another company located in Schio – CSC Spa - also produced the helium tanks for this project. However, these were smaller contracts and less technologically demanding.

Both companies were contracted to produce the same type of cavities, with each company responsible for producing half of the total number. The only difference was the choice for the final surface treatment step. Research Instruments GmbH used electrochemical polishing, whereas E. Zanon chose buffered chemical polishing for this last step.

The production was shared for two reasons. Firstly, companies wanted to develop their own expertise and infrastructure for the entire production process. Secondly, having two independent production facilities minimized the effects of potential disruptions in the

production process. The production supervision was also shared: Milan's Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) branch supervised E. Zanon, whereas DESY oversaw the production at Research Instrument GmbH.

Two options were considered for these contracts: "build to print" and "performance guarantee" (Singer et al., 2016). As this was the first time these firms were responsible for the entire production of SRF cavities, the selected suppliers added a significant premium to the second option. To reduce the costs, DESY decided to go for the "build to print" contract. Although the companies did not disclose the agreement's details, the selling price for each SRF cavity for other projects was approximately 100 000 euros. This suggests that each contract was worth around 40 million euros.

The industrial production of SRF cavities required broad knowledge transfer from DESY and INFN to the suppliers. As part of the contract with DESY, the infrastructure at both companies was upgraded to meet the necessary requirements for the surface treatment of the cavities. The two companies were advised by the two research organizations to purchase the new machinery and received training on how to use the latest equipment. Some of the new infrastructures included: new ISO4 and ISO7 cleanrooms, slow pumping/cold venting vacuum units, an ethanol rinsing facility, a wash system for bringing cavities into the cleanroom, a new high-vacuum oven for 800 degrees Celsius annealing of niobium cavities (Singer et al. 2016). The contracts also required that both companies had a few specialised roles, such as a physicist, a chemist and a material scientist, and E. Zanon had to hire new staff to fulfil this specific requirement.

Staff at the two firms and the RIs involved defined the XFEL project as a "game-changer": due to the costly infrastructure upgrade and training received, the gap between these two companies and other competitors had increased, giving them a competitive advantage when bidding for new contracts. Both companies received other SRF cavities contracts after XFEL.

Looking at the features of the agreement, the "build to print" contract meant that the production of the cavities had to meet strict XFEL specifications. To meet the stringent requirements, a comprehensive production monitoring system was implemented.

The central monitoring actions consisted of work according to a well-defined Quality Control (QC) Plan, internal Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Management system (QMS), and monthly progress reports (Singer et al., 2016). In addition, a project meeting took place at the company sites on average once per month, with visits to the companies by the DESY and INFN SRF cavities experts. On top of this, the two research institutes carried out an additional QC. Figure 1 illustrates the various steps we have just described.

Figure 1: Overview of procurement and production processes for XFEL

Source: Based on information from [Pagani \(2012\)](#), [Singer et al. \(2013\)](#), and input from INFN and DESY staff.

Overall, this indicates constant knowledge flows between the different organizations. Although both firms mentioned that HEP was not the most profitable business, they confirmed that the expertise acquired during this partnership was valuable for further contracts. The two companies also valued the new contacts acquired due to this collaboration.

When looking at the manufacturing process, conference proceedings and interviews revealed that the production almost entirely happened within the boundaries of the two firms with little involvement of subcontractors. DESY sourced the high-purity niobium and shipped it to the two manufacturers (Singer et al., 2016). Looking at the different production steps, only the low-added initial production phases - part of the deep drawing from the niobium sheets - were outsourced to other local Italian and German firms. Figure 2 illustrates these different production steps. Overall, the low involvement of subcontractors suggests that most of the direct benefits accrued to the two firms. This might have implications for the regional impact.

Figure 2: SRF cavities production steps

Source: Based on information from [Pagani \(2012\)](#), [Singer et al. \(2013\)](#), and input from INFN and DESY staff.

2.4 E. Zanon and Schio: the selection of the regional case study

Both companies involved in the SRF cavities production for XFEL have a long history of working in HEP. E. Zanon was established in 1919 in Schio in the province of Vicenza (Italy).² It was only in the 1970s that E. Zanon started its activity in scientific research. E. Zanon entered the HEP business in the 1990s when it produced its first niobium cavities as part of the collaboration with Ansaldo. It then acquired Ansaldo HEP business. In 2020, the HEP branch of E. Zanon was acquired by SIMIC. Zanon Research & Innovation was created. SIMIC mentioned E. Zanon experience in SRF cavities as one of the main reasons for the acquisition (Greco, 2021).³

Research Instruments GmbH was established in 2009 by the core team of ACCEL Instruments GmbH and Interatom, two companies that already operated in the field. These two companies have worked in the SRF cavities production business since 1995. The insights from our interviews revealed that the two companies differ in size. **E. Zanon has only one branch that focuses on High-Energy Physics, located in Schio (Vicenza), in Italy. In 2010, when the contract was assigned, it counted around 30 employees, and another additional 30 employees were hired to fulfil the contract. All the personnel at the company branch were involved in the contract.**

² It initially started as a small workshop that manufactured tanks for the thriving local textile industry.

³ Interviews with industry experts revealed that other companies operating in E. Zanon sector and in the same industrial district were also acquired by larger companies.

With around 280 employees, **Research Instruments** is bigger than E. Zanon Physics branch. It has two sites: the corporate headquarters are in Bergisch Gladbach, and the other site is in Dortmund. Unlike E. Zanon, it **did not have to recruit additional professional roles as part of the contracts**. Looking at the staff involved in the XFEL project, interviews revealed that **one third of the personnel were engaged in producing the SRF cavities for this contract**. The company has a more diversified business strategy, and HEP represents only a part of its business.

The fact that E. Zanon has only one site and all its personnel was involved in the contract make it an ideal case to test our approach, as it is easier to attribute any potential effect to the procurement contract. In contrast, had we looked at Research Instruments GmbH, we would not have been able to isolate the European XFEL contract's impact from other concurrent ones.

As a result of our choice to focus on E. Zanon, this study attempts to estimate the impact of the XFEL procurement contract on the municipality of Schio, where E. Zanon is located. Schio is a municipality of around 38 000 inhabitants, located in the province of Vicenza, in the Veneto region (see

Figure 3). At the same time, our initial assumption is that the effect is concentrated in the municipality of Schio, to account for the location of the E. Zanon plant at the edge of the administrative boundary (see Figure 4) and the possibility that effects go beyond the municipality, we also look at the wider Labour Market Area (LMA) as a unit of analysis. This geography is defined by ISTAT (Italian National Statistical Office) using commuting patterns, and it is supposed to capture most of the socio-economic relations in the area.⁴ Schio's LMA 2011 definition includes 17 other neighbouring municipalities (see

⁴ Labour market areas are sub-regional geographical areas where the bulk of the labour force lives and works, and where establishments can find the main part of the labour force necessary to occupy the offered jobs. They are function regions that are constructed by aggregating smaller geographical units, such as municipalities.

Figure 5). However, as the geographical unit of analysis gets larger, the effect of the contract might be harder to detect for two reasons. Firstly, the impact might be diluted over a wider area. In other words, while the contract is large relative to the size of the municipality, it becomes less so when looking at the LMA. Secondly, we might also be capturing concurrent shocks that affected other municipalities within the same LMA. If negative, these could offset the impact of the SRF procurement. If positive, the effect that we observed cannot solely be attributed to the contract. Despite these limitations, looking at different geographical levels can shed light on how widely these potential socio-economic benefits spread.

Figure 3: Schio is located in the province of Vicenza, in the north-eastern Italian region of Veneto.

3. Approach

This section outlines the approach we use to identify and measure the regional and local economic impacts that the procurement activities of large-scale research infrastructures set up as globally distributed projects can generate, beyond the benefits that directly accrue to the specific supplier (i.e. outside the boundaries of the firm).

In the rest of this section, firstly, we briefly discuss the conceptual framework and the mechanisms through which we expect these wider benefits to materialize. Secondly, we provide an overview of the Trajectory Balancing method and its application for this study. Thirdly, we describe the data we used for our analysis.

3.1 Conceptual framework

To identify the mechanisms through which RI procurement contracts might affect the local economy, we build on Moretti's (2010) local multiplier. In the context of science funding, the additional advantage of this approach is that it helps understand RI procurement's impact beyond the potential innovative output (e.g. measured by patents or total factor productivity) on which most existing studies have focused.

As in Moretti (2010), we consider the multiplier effects within the general equilibrium framework. Labour is mobile across regions and sectors of the economy (see Osman and Kemeney (2022) for an overview). Similarly to Dotti et al. (2021), we divided employment into three categories: supplier's industry, linked sectors, and consumption. We identified the linked sectors using Input-Output tables. All industry sectors in one economy are linked with one another. One industry purchases materials from other industries as input and processes them to produce goods and services. While part of these goods and services supply final-demand sectors, such as households, governments, and businesses, others are sold to other industries as raw materials for production. Input-Output tables summarise these links. In this framework, the definition of the linked sectors includes the industries within the region with the largest upstream output multiplier coefficient, which provide inputs to the supplier. The advantage of using this definition rather than Moretti's original tradable one is that it offers more clarity on how these potential wider effects are activated. The consumption sector is analogous to the non-tradable one in Moretti's (2010) original definition. According to our framework, we have three effects: employment effect on the supplier's industry, effects on linked sectors and local consumption. Figure 6 summarises these mechanisms. We discuss these in turn.

Figure 6: Local economic impact mechanisms – Employment effects on supplier's industry, effects on linked sectors, effects on consumption sector.

3.11 Employment effects on the supplier's industry beyond the boundaries of the firm

According to Public Procurement for Innovation (PPI) literature, **the contract can guarantee a significant production level and reduce uncertainty, allowing firms to benefit from economies of scale and technological investment and ensuring larger profits** (Uyarra and Flanaga, 2010). This can lead to an increase in labour demand, and **the effect is a rise in employment and wages in that particular industry.**

The magnitude of these direct effects will depend on the size of the contract, the type of product supplied (how labour-intensive it is) and the features of the production process. In the context of RI procurement, **two factors could amplify the increase in labour demand originating from the contract. One is the subsequent commercialisation of products or processes supplied.** If these find applications beyond RI, the effect is likely to be positive and large as more workers will be employed to satisfy the growing demand. **The other is reputation:** being selected by organisations such as CERN or DESY can signal quality and reliability to other firms and RIs (Castelnovo et al. 2018). For example, both companies that produced SRF cavities for XFEL subsequently won other RI procurement contracts. And it might not just be the supplier to benefit from this reputation effect, as winning this type of procurement contract might signal the quality of local technological capabilities. This could attract new contracts from other public and private organisations for the original suppliers and

firms within the same industry and local area, leading to a virtuous cycle. These direct effects can be captured by the change in the number of jobs in the suppliers' industry after the treatment over and above the jobs directly created by the beneficiary firm in order to fulfil the initial procurement contract.

Hypothesis 1: RI procurement contracts positively affect local employment in the suppliers' industry beyond the firm boundaries.

3.12 Employment effects on linked sectors

The procurement contract might also impact local employment in other linked sectors in two main ways. Firstly, **the contract can increase the demand for intermediate goods and services**. Manufacturing is at the heart of the value chain, and it can stimulate growth in sectors both upstream and downstream. The magnitude of these local effects is likely to be mediated by the initial expansion in the supplier's industry. And the spatial concentration of these impacts is likely to be determined by how localized the backward and forward linkages are.

Secondly, **the increased production in the impacted sectors may result in more agglomeration**. The clustering of economic activities literature suggests that industries with a strong input-output relationship tend to co-locate (Porter, 1998). These specialised firms might act as an anchor in developing a new cluster, signalling the local technological capabilities and attracting other firms that operate in the same linked industries (Feldman, 2003). However, these agglomeration effects might take a long time to materialise and cannot be captured in the short-term.

In this study, **these effects can be measured by the change in the number of jobs in these linked sectors**. However, it is important to note that backward and forward linkages tend to be stronger within the same macro sector, in this case, manufacturing. This makes it more challenging to differentiate between direct and indirect effects in the absence of granular sectoral data. In addition, we do not know the overall spatial distribution of these forward and backward linkages. However, these tend to be stronger within the same region.

Hypothesis 2: RI procurement contracts positively impact employment in the linked sectors within the local area

3.13 Employment effects on local consumption

There could also be an impact on local consumption through the local spending of people who have gained employment in the supplier's industry or linked sectors. The number of jobs in restaurants, retail and other local services increases because there are more workers in the area, and existing ones earn higher wages. In addition, there could also be an increase in business visitors, which could increase the demand for local services further. The change in the number of jobs in these industries can measure these effects on local consumption. Moretti (2010) argues that the size of this effect depends on three forces. Firstly, it depends on the type of new jobs created through the direct impact. The evidence suggests that high-skilled jobs have a larger multiplier effect as they pay higher wages, creating greater demand for local services (Moretti 2010). Secondly, the effect depends on consumer preferences and the technology in local services. More labour-intensive industries might experience a larger increase. Thirdly, the multiplier effect on local consumption might also depend on the local labour elasticity. The rise in labour demand and wages in the sector to which the procurement was assigned might crowd out jobs in other industries, potentially leading to a fall in the supply of local services.

It is complex to identify the location of this consumption and, therefore, the effect on local employment as we need to account for commuting flows. In other words, workers might spend their wages in the area where they work or live (Dotti et al. 2021). However, having information on employees' residences is not always possible. One way to overcome this challenge is to assume that employees spend their money where they work. An alternative would be to look at different geographies that consider these wider commuting patterns.

Hypothesis 3: RI procurement contracts positively affect employment in local services.

3.2 Methodology

This study aims to estimate the additional local economic impact of a RI procurement contract over and above what would have happened in its absence. **To establish this causal relationship between the contract and the local economic impact, one would need to compare the treated unit, in our case Schio, with a suitable counterfactual.** In an ideal scenario, this comparison would involve a "control group" composed of other municipalities with similar characteristics. However, due to the complex technical requirements and low level of commercialization, only two companies in the world produce SRF cavities on a large scale. This means that E. Zanon's location choice might be endogenous. In other words, E. Zanon chose to locate or stay in Schio because of the local technological capabilities, which might affect the local economic performance. The presence of specialised firms might make the

industrial profile of these places different from the rest, making it harder to find a control group. In addition, popular methods such as difference-in-difference do not perform well when only a small number of units are treated (Conly and Taber, 2011).

Given this context, **the trajectory balancing method (TBM)**, developed by Hazlett and Xu (2018), **is the most suitable to address this challenge**. TBM is a general reweighting approach for causal inference that builds on the synthetic control method (SCM), introduced initially by Abadie et al. (2003). Like SCM, it is based on the idea that when the units of observation are a small number of aggregate entities, a combination of unaffected units provides a more appropriate comparison than any single unaffected unit alone. **TBM creates a synthetic unit by searching for a weighted combination of control units to approximate the pre-treatment trajectory of the outcome variable for the treated unit.**⁵

TBM estimates the effect of the treatment, in our case, the procurement contract, by comparing the evolution of the outcome variable of interest for the unit affected by the treatment to the evolution of the same outcome variable for a synthetic control. The intuition behind TBM is that if the trajectory of the outcome variable of interest is similar for both the synthetic and the treated unit before the treatment, any discrepancy we observe post-treatment can be attributed to the policy change. In this study, any difference between Schio and the “synthetic” Schio after the production started could be attributed to the XFEL procurement contract.⁶

Using TBM we create a synthetic Schio by choosing weights for each of the other municipalities in the sample so that the trajectory of the outcome variable and other characteristics are approximately equal in the pre-treatment period. TBM assigns a set of non-negative weights W so that the sum equals one. In this case, the causal effect – average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) - for different outcome variables is given by:

$$\theta_{Schio,t} = Y_{Schio,t} - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} w_i Y_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Where $Y_{i,t}$ is the outcome variable of interest observed for municipality i in the donor pool after 2012, and w_i is the synthetic control weights. As the main result, we report the average effect across years to reduce the noise from fluctuations over time.

⁵ Compared to SCM, TBM has two main advantages. Firstly, it allows achieving balance on the full trajectory of the pre-treatment outcomes rather than their average levels. Thus, the reweighted control units are much more similar in their joint distribution of pre-treatment variables to the treated group than what can be ensured when using the SCM. It does so by using kernel and mean balancing. Secondly, the balancing approach also works when we have shorter pre-treatment periods.

⁶ The assumption here is that subsequent procurement contracts are a result of the initial one.

This method represents a novel approach to studying RI's local economic impact as it is the first time that SCM-methods have been adopted to estimate the local effect of RI procurement. One of the main advantages of this method is that it can be easily replicated for different kinds of contracts, regions and RIs to understand the heterogeneity of these effects and the mediating role of other factors.

3.3 Data

We use two main geographical units for this study. Firstly, we use municipalities, the most detailed level of stratification possible. Secondly, we use the LMA, a geographical area defined by ISTAT that considers commuting patterns.

We use a panel dataset covering the 2004-17 period, stemming from different data sources, to carry out the analysis.

- The data on the number of employees for the 2004-17 period comes from the ISTAT Statistical Register of active enterprises (ASIA) (ISTAT, 2022). This provides data on the number of employees at the municipality and LMA levels, broken down by ATECO industry sections (*Attività Economiche*). This is the Italian national version of the NACE (*Nomenclature Générale des Activités Économiques dans les Communautés Européennes*) classification adopted by the European Union (ISTAT, 2022; Colasanti et al., 2009).
- We then use information from the EUREGIO database (European Commission, Joint Research Centre, 2020), a novel global input-output database with regional details for EU countries, to identify which sectors are linked to the one in which E. Zanon operates. This database provides this information at the NUTS2 level. In this case, the data we use is for the Veneto region, where Schio is located.
- The two datasets, the ASIA and the EUREGIO databases use different industry aggregations. Table 1 shows the crosswalks between these different definitions and the local multiplier categorization.
- The employment data is only available for the entire period at the industry section level. To investigate the impact within the manufacturing sector, we use the OECD (2021) Input-Output tables at the national level to identify the 2-digit industries upstream to E. Zanon. We then use data on turnover aggregated from Orbis (Bureau van Dijk, 2021) at the municipality level to calculate the local effect on the upstream industries. We closely follow Kaleml-Ozcan et al. (2019) and undertake a series of cleaning steps. These are summarized in Appendix B.
- To build a synthetic Schio, we use the following predictors: population density, employment rate, population change between 2001 and 2011, and the share of the population with a degree at the municipality level from the Italian Census 2011 (ISTAT

2022). We also include data on local wages that we calculated using taxable income from employment that comes from the IRPEF (*Imposta sul reddito delle persone fisiche*) dataset (Ministero dell' Economia e delle Finanze, 2022).

- We take a series of steps to ensure that the control units in the donor pool resemble Schio as closely as possible. These steps are described in Appendix B.

Table 1: ATECO 2007- EURegio database industry matching.

ATECO 2007	EUREGIO database	Local multiplier categorization
Manufacturing	Food, Beverage & Tobacco	Manufacturing
Manufacturing	Textile and leather	Manufacturing
Manufacturing	Coke, refined petroleum, nuclear, fuel and chemicals	Manufacturing
Manufacturing	Electrical & Optical equipment, transport equipment	Manufacturing
Manufacturing	Other manufacturing	Manufacturing
Construction	Construction	Consumption
Wholesale & Retail	Distribution	Linked-sector
Hotels & Restaurant	Hotels & Restaurant	Consumption
Transport	Transport & Storage	Linked-sector
Finance	Financial Intermediation	Linked-sector
Business activities	Real Estate, renting and business activities	Linked-sector

4. Results

This section reports the causal effects of the XFEL contract on Schio's local employment. We begin by estimating the effect at the municipality level for the three sectors. To understand the spatial spread of these effects, we also look at the LMA. We then conduct some robustness tests to check the validity of the results. Finally, we test the presence of spillovers on neighbouring municipalities.

4.1 Impact on municipalities

To estimate the impact on the three sectors at the municipality level, we construct a synthetic Schio as a weighted average of other local areas in the donor pool.

Table 2 reports the municipalities and individual weights used to construct the three synthetic versions.⁷

⁷ The municipalities used to construct the synthetic Schio for the other two control variables are different. This is due to the fact that the algorithm uses the outcome variable in the pre-treatment period to create the counterfactual.

Table 2: Control group for manufacturing, linked-sectors, consumption - municipality.

	MUNICIPALITY	MANUFACTURING WEIGHTS
1	Cornaredo	0.19
2	Belluno	0.19
3	Trezzano sul Naviglio	0.13
4	Treviglio	0.10
5	Lainate	0.08
6	Martellago	0.07
7	Senago	0.06
8	Sagraate	0.06
9	Paderno Dugnano	0.03
10	Mariano Comense	0.03
	MUNICIPALITY	LINKED-SECTOR WEIGHTS
1	Castiglione delle Stiviere	0.15
2	Giussano	0.07
3	Cornaredo	0.06
4	Voghera	0.06
5	Rozzano	0.06
6	Castelfranco Veneto	0.05
7	Cormano	0.05
8	Chiavari	0.03
9	Gorizia	0.03
10	Vittorio Veneto	0.03
	MUNICIPALITY	CONSUMPTION WEIGHTS
1	Venaria Reale	0.47
2	Abbiategrosso	0.06
3	Sassuolo	0.05
4	Bra	0.05
5	Imperia	0.05
6	Castelfranco Veneto	0.05
7	San Lazzaro di Savena	0.04
8	Gorizia	0.03
9	Montebelluna	0.03
10	Casale Monferrato	0.02

Table 3 reports the covariate balance in the pre-treatment period (before the production started in 2012) and the average 141 municipalities in the donor pool for the three outcome variables. It confirms that the synthetic Schio is a closer fit for the comparison. However, the synthetic version for manufacturing seems to better match Schio in the pre-treatment period than for the other two sectors.

Table 3: Balance table – municipality.

	Schio	Avr. Northern municipalities	Synthetic Schio
Manufacturing			
(Log) Avr. employee income (2004-12)	9.92	9.95	9.93
Pop. (2011)	39131.00	30619.23	38926.62
Pop. density (2011)	591.10	1366.64	559.93
% of high-skilled pop. (2011)	35.20	33.28	34.70
Pop. change (2001-11)	0.40	0.60	0.42
Employment Rate (2011)	48.30	49.93	48.18
Linked-sectors			
(Log) Manufacturing employees (2004-12)	8.93	7.84	8.27
(Log) Avr. employee income (2004-12)	9.92	9.95	9.95
(Log) Consumption employees (2004-12)	7.31	7.31	7.63
Pop. (2011)	39131.00	30619.23	40456.96
% of high-skilled pop. (2011)	35.20	33.28	35.47
Employment rate (2011)	48.3	49.93	50.30
Pop. change (2001-11)	0.40	0.60	0.71
Consumption			
(Log) Avr. employees income (2004-12)	9.92	9.95	9.95
(Log) Manufacturing employees (2004-12)	8.93	7.84	8.47
Pop. (2011)	39131.00	30619.23	40340.20
Pop. density (2011)	591.10	1366.64	1043.79
% of high-skilled pop. (2011)	35.20	33.28	36.00
Pop. change (2001-11)	0.40	0.60	0.44
Employment rate (2011)	48.30	49.93	49.19

Figure 7 shows the trajectory of the number of employees in the three sectors for Schio and its synthetic version. We discuss the three effects in turn.

4.11 Manufacturing

Panel a in Figure 7 shows that for manufacturing, the two trajectories closely match before the beginning of production. The estimates of the effect of the contract on the manufacturing sector are given by the difference between Schio and the synthetic version. In 2012, when production started, a gap between the number of manufacturing employees in Schio and its synthetic version started to emerge. While the number of employees falls for both Schio and the synthetic one, the fall for the latter is more pronounced. From 2013 onwards, the number of manufacturing employees gradually increases in Schio, whereas the number continues its downward trend for the synthetic counterfactual. This **evidence suggests that the procurement contract has softened the impact of the 2011 - 2014 crisis that negatively**

affected the Italian economy: over this period, the number of employees in the manufacturing sector in Italy fell by 6.8% (ISTAT, 2017). The trajectory of the synthetic Schio reproduces this national trend.

Figure 7: Trends in the number of employees for manufacturing (a), linked sectors (b) and consumption (c) by municipality.

To check whether the effects on manufacturing are statistically significant, we follow Abadie et al. (2015) and run an in-space placebo test. This consists of reassigning the treatment to each unit in the donor pool. The effect is considered statistically significant if it is large relative to the distribution of the placebo effects. We calculate the ratios between the Root Mean Square Prediction Error (RMSPE) before and after the treatment for all the other units in the donor pool, the outcome variable. RMSPE measures the size of the gap in the outcome variable between the municipalities and their respective synthetic. A large post and pre-treatment periods ratio indicates that the effect is statistically significant. Figure 8 shows that for manufacturing, the gap for Schio is the second largest RMSPE ratio after Thiene. However, Thiene shows a large negative trend compared to its counterfactual.

Figure 8: Ratio of Post-2012 RMSPE to Pre-2012 RMSPE: Schio and Top 50 Control Municipalities with the largest ratio.

Overall, our results suggest a positive and statistically significant effect on the number of manufacturing employees: over the 2012 - 2017 period, the number of manufacturing employees was approximately 5% higher than the synthetic Schio on average.

By 2017, the number of employees in the manufacturing sector in Schio was approximately 7% (+475) higher than the synthetic Schio. Around 30 of these new jobs were added by E. Zanon. This suggests that every job added by the supplier supported approximately 15 additional jobs in the manufacturing sector in Schio.

The user-supplier linkages tend to be stronger within the same sector, which is the case for manufacturing in Veneto. Hence, from these results, it is unclear whether this effect is driven by an increase in demand for final products or input produced by the rest of the manufacturing sector due to the lack of granular data for the period before the production started and for the many municipalities in the post-treatment period. However, we can look at this more granular data on manufacturing for Schio using two-digit industry NACE codes. Figure 8 shows that the industry in which E. Zanon operates (code 28) experienced a fall in the number of employees, whereas “Metal production” (code 25) grew the most. While these changes cannot be interpreted as causal, they suggest that the better performance of Schio’s manufacturing sector is likely to be driven by the rise in demand for inputs.

Figure 9: Change in manufacturing employees 2012 - 2019, by sub-industry, Schio.

To further unpack this impact on the manufacturing sector, we do the following. Firstly, we use the Input-Output tables at the national level produced by the OECD (2021). The benefit of using national tables is that they provide more detailed information at the sectorial links and this helps identify those sector divisions within manufacturing that are upstream to E. Zanon's one. The main assumption here is that there is no substantial difference between the industrial linkages in Schio and those in the rest of Italy. An inspection of these tables reveals that Metal products (NACE code 25) is the division with the largest multiplier coefficients. This is the sector that experienced the largest increase in employment in the 2012 - 2019 period, as shown in

Figure 9.

Secondly, to overcome the lack of granular data on employment, we use the Orbis database (Bureau van Dijk, 2021), which contains firms' financial statements and their activity in terms of sales, turnover, and detailed information on their location, industry and ownership.⁸ As the Orbis data on the number of employees is limited, we calculate the average turnover by municipality, industry, and year using the operating turnover revenue variable.⁹ We again use the TBM to construct a synthetic Schio and estimate the effect on the average turnover in the Manufacture of basic metal products.¹⁰

Figure 10 shows **that a gap in average turnover between Schio and its synthetic version begins to emerge after the treatment year**. The in-space placebo test reveals that this effect is statistically significant at the 5% level – the second highest RMSPE ratio. These results and the descriptive evidence presented in

⁸ Orbis data tends to be more representative of large firms and of those in the manufacturing sector. See Bajgar et al. (2020) and Kalemli-Özcan, et al. (2019) for a more detailed discussion of this issue.

¹⁰ The sample for this estimation includes 56 municipalities, including Schio.

Figure 9, suggest a positive supply-chain effect within the manufacturing sector.

Figure 10: Trends in average turnover for metal products, by municipality.

4.12 Linked sectors

After discussing the effect on manufacturing, we look at the impact on linked sectors. Panel b in Figure 7 shows the trajectory of the number of employees in the linked sectors for Schio and its synthetic version. In this case, synthetic Schio performs better than Schio in the post-treatment period. However, the placebo test reveals that **the effect on the linked sectors is statistically non-significant**.¹¹ There are several potential explanations for the lack of effect. Firstly, the pre-treatment match between Schio and its synthetic version is not so close and therefore, it is possible that we are not able to capture any discrepancy between the two. Secondly, the definition of linked sectors might be too broad and include industries that are not directly linked to E. Zanon. The sectorial links in Schio might differ from those in the rest of the region. To check whether these results are susceptible to our categorisation, we repeat the same exercise using different definitions and individual sectors. However, the results are also statistically non-significant. Thirdly, it might be the case that the increase in the labour demand for the manufacturing sector generates an increase in labour costs. This has a negative effect on other sectors that are exposed to competition from outside the area. This is what Moretti's (2010) framework hypothesized for the rest of the tradable sector. Fourthly, RIs often set up consortia involving firms and research centres in different regions and countries for large and technologically intensive contracts. This was the case for SRF cavities production for XFEL. And even for the following contract with ITER, E. Zanon was part of a consortium. In some instances, firms continue to collaborate with partners in the consortium even after fulfilling these contracts. As a result, **the inter-industry linkages are not localized, and the effect cannot be detected by focusing on the treated area**. The interviews with firms and local industry experts revealed that **firms that work in these international scientific projects tend to have weak links with other local companies**.

4.13 Consumption

After looking at the effect on manufacturing and linked sectors, we examine whether the jobs in the manufacturing sector had an impact on local consumption, one of the main claims of Moretti's framework. Panel c in Figure 7 shows that a gap began to appear in 2012. Between 2016 and 2017, there was a sharp increase for Schio. Our interviews suggested that the rise can be mainly attributed to the *Superstrada Pedemontana Veneto* rather than the contract. This new toll road increased the accessibility to the municipalities of the Vicenza area, including Schio. The placebo test shows that **the effect on consumption employment is statistically non-significant**.¹² We also used alternative definitions of the consumption sector

¹¹ Schio had the 116th highest RMSPE ratio.

¹² Schio had the 101st highest RMSPE ratio.

and look at the effect on individual sectors. But the results were all statistically non-significant (see Appendix C). The lack of impact on the consumption sector could be explained by the use of the municipality as the unit of analysis. Commuting flows might influence how and where income is used for consumption (Dotti et al. 2021). Schio might attract workers from neighbouring areas, and these commuters might be spending in the place where they live rather than where they work. We investigate this possibility in the next section.

4.2 Impact on Labour Market Areas

Procurement contracts might have spillover effects on neighbouring municipalities. On the one hand, firms located in the surrounding areas might benefit from the boost in demand for this technology. This would imply that the effects are much larger than what we have so far estimated by focusing on the municipality. On the other hand, such contracts might have altered the structure of location incentives for more mobile firms and households and triggered the substitution of economic activity from the surrounding to Schio. This could be due, for example, to benefit from agglomeration effects. In other words, the increase in employment documented in this section might have occurred at the expense of other areas. Other studies that evaluated the impact of place-based policies found the presence of negative spillovers (Hanson and Rohlin, 2013; Andini and de Blasio, 2016). **To investigate the impact on neighbouring areas, we use a larger unit for our analysis, the LMA.** We follow a similar process to the one in Section 4.1

Table 4 shows the LMAs used to construct the synthetic version for the three outcome variables. The balance table (

Table 5) indicates that the synthetic version is a close match for the comparison for the three sectors.

Table 4: Control group for manufacturing, linked-sectors, consumption - LMA.

	LMA	MANUFACTURING WEIGHTS
1	Salo'	0.09
2	Chiari	0.07
3	Badia	0.07
4	Cesenatico	0.06
5	Jesolo	0.04
6	Pordenone	0.02
7	Savigliano	0.02
8	San Bonifacio	0.02
9	Arzignano	0.02
10	Castiglione delle Stiviere	0.02
	LMA	LINKED-SECTOR WEIGHTS
1	Sassuolo	0.37
2	Vignola	0.21
3	Grumello del Monte	0.16
4	Cittadella	0.12
5	Manerbio	0.05
6	Cles	0.03
7	Castelfranco Veneto	0.03
8	Modena	0.02
9	Correggio	0.01
10	Lumezzane	0.01
	LMA	CONSUMPTION WEIGHTS
1	Grumello del Monte	0.31
2	Ovada	0.20
3	Sassuolo	0.16
4	Lecco	0.13
5	Thiene	0.11
6	San Bonifacio	0.06
7	Bassano del Grappa	0.01
8	Arzignano	0.01
9	Busto Arsizio	0.01
10	Como	0.01

Table 5: Balance table - LMAs.

	Schio	Average LMAs	Synthetic Schio (TBM)
(Log) Consumption employees (2004-12)	8.35	8.10	8.35
Pop. (2011)	105684.00	118112.31	105684.00
% of high-skilled population (2011)	8226.00	12988.18	8226.00
Buildings for commercial use (2011)	2760.00	3233.10	2760.00
Linked-sectors			
(Log) Manufacturing employees (2004-12)	9.81	8.37	9.84
Pop. (2011)	13210.50	14764.04	14069.29
% of high-skilled population (2011)	8226.00	12988.18	8813.68
Buildings for commercial use (2011)	2760.00	3233.10	2504.84
Consumption			
(Log) Manufacturing employees (2004-12)	105684.00	118112.31	118366.49
Pop. (2011)	9.81	8.37	9.63
% of high-skilled population (2011)	8226.00	12988.18	9515.41
Buildings for commercial use (2011)	2760.00	3233.10	2680.11

4.21 Manufacturing

Panel a in

Figure 11 shows that the effect on manufacturing at the LMA is positive. The trajectory is similar to the one for the municipality shown in Section 4.11, suggesting that the procurement contract might have made the sector more resilient even at the LMA level. However, the placebo test reveals that **the effect on manufacturing employment is statistically non-significant**.¹³ Two potential reasons can explain these statistically non-significant effects. Firstly, the effect might be diluted over a wider area (attenuation); secondly, there might be negative spillovers. We investigate this in Section 4.4

¹³ Schio's RMSPE ratio was the 127th highest.

Figure 11: Trends in the number of employees for manufacturing (a), linked sectors (b) and consumption (c) by LMA.

4.22 Linked sectors

We also look at the impact on the other two sectors. Panels b in

Figure 11 shows the effect on the linked sectors. Schio seems to perform worse than its synthetic version with a gap emerging after the beginning of the production in 2012. Overall, **the effect on employment in linked sectors over the time period is negative but statistically non-significant**, and this is in line with what we found at the municipality level.

4.23 Consumption

Panel c in Figure 8 shows the effects on the consumption sector at the LMA level, which considers these commuting patterns. **The effect on employment in consumption is positive, but even in this case, it is statistically non-significant.**¹⁴ The lack of effect on the consumption sector at both geographical levels is in contrast with Moretti's work and other studies replicating the local multiplier framework (Kemeney and Osman, 2022). Two possible explanations can account for this. Firstly, the increase in manufacturing employment might still have led to a rise in local consumption, but this has not translated into more jobs. There are other ways to address an increase in demand, such as increasing the hours or productivity of existing workers. Secondly, Moretti (2010) and other studies replicating this framework looked at long-term changes. In this study, we only looked at the 5-year impact of this procurement contract. Other studies that have applied the local multiplier framework in Italy and looked at a longer timeframe also found a statistically non-significant effect on local services (Auricchio 2015; Blasio and Menon 2012). De Blasio and Menon (2012) attribute this lack of impact to two features of the Italian economy. Firstly, Italy's economy is characterised by a higher degree of anti-competitive regulation in the service sector. Because of this lack of competition, the increase in demand for local services and goods generated by the new jobs in manufacturing might have translated into higher prices rather than higher supply. Secondly, a national wage bargaining system means wages react less to changes in labour market conditions. This can have a negative effect on labour mobility as wages do not adjust enough to attract workers from other areas.

¹⁴ Schio's RMPSE ratio was the 106th highest.

4.3 Robustness checks

As suggested by Abadie and L'Hour (2021) and Cerqua and Di Stefano (2022), to check how sensitive our results are to the research design choices, we conduct a series of robustness tests:

1. We backdate the treatment to 2008– in-time placebo test.
2. We run a leave-one-out analysis to assess whether the results are sensitive to the choice of units in the donor pool. This consists of running the trajectory balancing, excluding the ten municipalities that were assigned the largest weights in the original estimation from the sample one at a time, and taking the average of these estimates.

The robustness checks produce estimates (see Table 6) **similar to the main specification**. When we backdate the effect to 2008, the estimates are higher than the main results, but they are statistically non-significant for all sectors. The leave-one-out estimates are also close to the main results, suggesting that specific weights do not drive our estimates.

Table 6: Robustness tests.

	(Log) Manufact.	(Log) Linked sectors	(Log) Consumption
Main estimate	0.05**	-0.04	0.01
Backdating - 4 years earlier	0.10	-0.09	0.03
Leave-one-out procedure	0.04	-0.04	-0.02

4.4 Displacement

Two potential explanations exist for the lack of impact on manufacturing employment found at the LMA level. Firstly, the effect can be diluted when moving to a wider area. **Although the contract is large, it is small relative to the size of the LMA**. Secondly, there could be negative spillovers (Andini and Blasio 2016). **Our estimated effects on manufacturing at the municipality level could be large because they represent local rather than national effects**. Local estimates would overstate national effects if, for example, labour was supplied elastically, and workers migrated from other locations. **Such an increase in local employment would come at the cost of reduced employment elsewhere**. Other studies examining the impact of place-based policies found displacement effects (Hanson and Rohlin, 2013; Andini and de Blasio, 2016).

To investigate this further, **we compare the untreated municipalities in Schio LMA with the untreated municipalities in other LMAs in our sample**, using the TBM in a difference-in-difference setting. This comparison follows a similar approach to the one by Hanson and Rohlin (2013) in their evaluation of the spillover effects on the US Federal Empowerment

Zones (EZs) and by Andini and de Blasio (2016) in their study of publicly financed investment projects in Italy.

The results, reported in Table 7, show that for manufacturing, the effect on the other municipalities in the LMA was positive but statistically non-significant. The effect on the other sectors was also statistically non-significant. Another possibility is that the procurement contract might have affected some neighbouring municipalities more than others. To further investigate the presence of negative spillovers, we decide to focus on the bordering municipalities with which Schio is likely to have the strongest links. We repeat the same exercise, using those municipalities that share a border with Schio as treated.¹⁵ The results are statistically non-significant for all three sectors.

This suggests that the extra jobs in Schio were not at the expense of other municipalities. However, we cannot exclude that there might be negative spillovers on areas outside Schio that are economically similar (Hanson and Rohlin, 2013). For example, other municipalities whose firms rely on the same customer base might have experienced a negative effect.

Table 7: Displacement effects on neighbouring municipalities.

	ATT	S.E.	z-score	CI.lower	CI.upper	p.value
Rest of municipalities in the LMA						
Manufacturing	0.10	0.10	1.01	-0.09	0.28	0.31
Linked-sectors	0.03	0.05	0.61	-0.06	0.12	0.54
Consumption	0.04	0.12	0.31	-0.20	0.27	0.76
Bordering municipalities						
Manufacturing	0.07	0.07	1.12	-0.05	0.20	0.26
Linked-sectors	0.05	0.04	1.14	-0.04	0.14	0.26
Consumption	0.04	0.04	0.97	-0.04	0.12	0.33

4.5 Comparison to other estimates in the literature

Although, to the best of our knowledge, **this is the first study to look at the causal local economic impact of RI procurement**, it is useful to compare our results with two other studies that investigated the local economic impact of public funding of R&D and science more broadly.

Kantar and Whalley (2022) found that **manufacturing employment in counties that received NASA procurement contracts grew by 13% on average** over the 1975-1992

¹⁵ The municipalities treated are Torrebelvicino, Valdagno, Valli del Pasubio, Velo d'Astico, Zane'. Marano Vicentino, Monte di Malo, Posina, Santorso, San Vito di Leguzzano.

period. This study looked at a longer-time period and this might explain why these effects are larger than what we found in our analysis.

Chhabra et al. (2019) examined changes in local employment as a response to public spending on R&D and science as part of the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act (ARRA). This included contracts, grants and loan awards, to businesses, institutions and individuals. Their study found that between 2009 and 2013, **each one million USD in R&D was associated with 27 additional jobs in the county** that received the funding and one job in adjacent counties, suggesting that the effects tend to be spatially concentrated. The impact found by Chhabra et al. (2019) is larger than those generated by the SRF procurement contracts that we analysed. This could be for three reasons. Firstly, Chhabra et al. (2019) looked at total employment whereas our analysis focused on selected sectors. Secondly, their estimates seem to include those jobs directly created by the suppliers. Finally, the primary objective of ARRA was to stimulate economic growth, whereas in the case of RI procurement, scientific discovery remains the main goal.

Overall, **our results are line with existing studies that showed a positive effect of public funding of science on local employment.**

5. Conclusions

This study provides new evidence on the local economic impact of RIs by examining the high-tech procurement channel. We leveraged a large contract for the European XFEL to understand whether this channel could generate economic benefits beyond the firm's boundaries. We focused on the municipality of Schio, where one of the suppliers for this contract is located.

While most of the past evaluations of the socio-economic benefits have focused on innovative outcomes, this study estimated the effect on local employment. To do this, we used an adapted version of Moretti's local multiplier framework. We divided employment into three sectors; manufacturing – the supplier's one –, the linked sectors – directly connected to the supplier's sector – and consumption. We use the TBM to test the hypotheses and construct a counterfactual synthetic Schio.

The results show that the **SRF supply contract greatly affected the local manufacturing sector.** By the end of the period, **the number of employees in manufacturing in Schio was approximately 7% higher than it would have been in the absence of the contract.** To give a magnitude of this effect, **for every job the supplier added to fulfil the contract, 15 more were supported in other local manufacturing firms. In monetary terms, 1 million euros worth of RI procurement, supported 11 additional jobs in manufacturing outside the boundaries of the supplier.** Further investigation suggests that **upstream industries to the supplier drove these results. The impact on manufacturing seems to be spatially concentrated:** the effect was statistically non-significant once we looked at the labour market area. A potential explanation for this lack of impact on the wider area is the presence of negative spillovers: jobs being displaced from neighbouring areas to Schio. However, further analysis reveals that this is not the case and that the effect of the contract is likely to have been diluted over the wider area.

The effect on the linked sectors was statistically non-significant. There are two potential explanations for this lack of impact. Firstly, these links between the supplier's industry and other sectors might not be strong. Secondly, the inter-industry **linkages for these types products in international cooperations are not spatially concentrated.** RIs typically set up consortia involving firms and research centres in different regions and countries for the largest and most technologically intensive contracts. This was the case for the SRF cavities production for XFEL. And even for a subsequent large contract, E. Zanon was part of a consortium and was one element in the entire value chain of the system to be supplied. These links may last well beyond the contract periods.

In contrast to other studies on the local multiplier, the **effect on local consumption was statistically non-significant**. This was also the case when we looked at the LMA, which takes into account commuting patterns. There are two potential explanations for this. Firstly, the positive impact on the manufacturing sector might have boosted demand for local services. However, given the limited contract volume this does not necessarily translate into higher employment in the consumption sector. Other mechanisms, such as higher productivity and longer hours, might satisfy such demand increase. Secondly, other studies have looked at a longer timeframe, whereas we have only looked at the short-term effect. However, other studies that have adopted the local multiplier in the context of Italy and looked at changes over decades also found no effect. Andini and De Blasio (2016) argue that a national bargaining system and anti-competition legislation make the Italian local labour market systems less reactive to shocks.

Our results are aligned with other studies that demonstrated a positive impact of scientific procurement on the local economy in which the supplier is located. However, the effects we identified are smaller than those found by Khantar and Whalley (2022) and Chhabra et al. (2019).

The findings of this paper have policy implications and offer insights for future research avenues. While the approach used in this paper guarantees the internal validity of our findings, as with any evaluation, the external validity of these results is limited and cannot be generalized to other RIs, contracts, regions and technologies. **The advantage of the proposed approach is that it can be applied to other cases to better understand the heterogeneity of such effects.** For example, it can be replicated to understand whether smaller and less-technological intensive contracts can also impact the local economy in which the supplier is located.

From a policymaking perspective, given that the most valuable contracts are assigned to high-tech manufacturing firms, **our results suggest that by only looking at the impact on the suppliers, we would underestimate the socio-economic impact of these projects.** Governments and policymakers should consider these wider effects when deciding on such investments. In addition, given the increasing importance of RIs for scientific progress, and with several large projects under construction, like the European Spallation Source, and like the Future Circular Collider for which this study has been carried out, RI procurement contracts can be a policy tool for national and local governments to promote economic development. The next report (LSE-RD -1.5/Doc) will develop key policy recommendation on how the FCC construction and operation project can generate regional benefits in those countries that participate as funding authorities and how RIs can be integrated in smart specialization strategies.

Appendix A: List of interviewees

Interviewee	Organization
Walter Venturini Delsonaro	CERN
Ed Daly	Jefferson Lab
John Rathke	AES
Ted Roark	Roarkfab
Michael Neumann	Formerly at DESY
Riko Wichmann	DESY
Hans Weise	DESY
Paolo Michelato	INFN Milano
Daniele Sertore	INFN Milano
Ambra Gresele	Zanon Research & Innovation
Michael Pekeler	Research Instruments GmbH
Marco Roveta	Criotec
Hendrie Derking	Cryoworld
Paolo Gurisatti	Unive – Ca' Foscari/ Fondazione Palazzo Festari

Appendix B: Data preparation steps

ORBIS Data

- Before using the Orbis data, we undertake a series of cleaning steps. We drop all the duplicate accounts of the same firm in the same year, using values that refer to the entire calendar year and excluding those observations that had missing values for the operating turnover variable. In addition, I deflated the series using the National GDP deflator from the World Bank (2021), with 2020 as the base year.

Data restrictions for the main panel

- To ensure that the control units in the donor pool resemble Schio as closely as possible and reduce interpolation bias, we include only the municipalities in Northern Italy with a population size close to Schio (50% more or 50% less than the Schio population). Focusing on this part of Italy gives a more homogenous sample as Southern Italy differs substantially from the North regarding market access, infrastructure, and cultural habits (Andini and de Blasio 2016). In addition, by excluding areas in the South, I reduce the possibility of concurrent place-based initiatives that tend to target Southern Italy and might bias the results. When it comes to Labour Market Areas, we include those in Northern Italy for the same reasons.
- To minimise the possibility that other units in the donor pool have received a similar treatment whose effect we are trying to investigate, we use CERN procurement data to exclude all the municipalities that have received large procurement contracts (larger than 1 million Swiss Francs) in the post-treatment period.
- To enforce the assumption of no spillover across units, we exclude the neighbouring municipalities in the same labour Market area. We do not impose the same restrictions when looking at LMAs. These areas are created using commuting flows and, therefore, should be more self-contained economies.

Appendix C: Impact on selected individual sectors

Table 8: Impact on hospitality, wholesale & retail, construction - municipality (2012-2017)

	ATT	RMSPE-rank	p-value
Hospitality employees	0.02	119	0.84
Wholesale & retail employees	-0.05	91	0.64
Construction employees	0.01	135	0.95

List of References

- 1) Abadie, Alberto, Alexis Diamond, and Jens Hainmueller. 2015. "Comparative Politics and the Synthetic Control Method." *American Journal of Political Science* 59 (2): 495–510. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12116>.
- 2) Abadie, Alberto, and Javier Gardeazabal. 2003. "The Economic Costs of Conflict: A Case Study of the Basque Country." *American Economic Review* 93 (1): 113–32. <https://doi.org/10.1257/000282803321455188>.
- 3) Abadie, Alberto, and Jérémy L'Hour. 2021. "A Penalized Synthetic Control Estimator for Disaggregated Data." *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 116 (536): 1817–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.2021.1971535>.
- 4) Andini, Monica, and Guido de Blasio. 2016. "Local Development That Money Cannot Buy: Italy's *Contratti Di Programma*." *Journal of Economic Geography* 16 (2): 365–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbu048>.
- 5) Auricchio, Marta. 2015. "Local Manufacturing Multiplier and Human Capital in Italian Local Labor Markets".
- 6) Bastianin, Andrea, Paolo Castelnovo, Massimo Florio, and Anna Giunta. 2022. "Big Science and Innovation: Gestation Lag from Procurement to Patents for CERN Suppliers." *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 47 (2): 531–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-021-09854-5>.
- 7) Bloom, Nicholas. 2020. "Are Ideas Getting Harder to Find?" *The American Economic Review* 110 (4): 41.
- 8) Bureau van Dijk. (April 27, 2017). Orbis Historical Data [Data set]. <https://orbis.bvdinfo.com/>
- 9) Castelnovo, Paolo, Massimo Florio, Stefano Forte, Lucio Rossi, and Emanuela Sirtori. 2018. "The Economic Impact of Technological Procurement for Large-Scale Research Infrastructures: Evidence from the Large Hadron Collider at CERN." *Research Policy* 47 (9): 1853–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.06.018>.
- 10) Cerqua, Augusto, and Roberta Di Stefano. 2022. "When Did Coronavirus Arrive in Europe?" *Statistical Methods & Applications* 31 (1): 181–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10260-021-00568-4>.
- 11) Chhabra, Yulia, Margaret Levenstein and Jason Owen-Smith. 2019. "The Local economic impact of science spending: evidence from the American Recovery and reinvestment act". *Ross School of Business Working Paper*. Working paper no.1383 April 2019.
- 12) Colasanti, Cecilia, Stefania Macchia, and Paola Vicari. 'The Automatic Coding of Economic Activities Descriptions for WEB Users'. *NTTS 2009 - New Techniques and Technologies for Statistics 2009*, 2009.
- 13) Crescenzi, Riccardo, Max Nathan and Andres Rodriguez-Pose. 2016. "Do inventors talk to strangers? On proximity and collaborative knowledge creation." *Research Policy* 45 (1):177-194.
- 14) Crescenzi, Riccardo, and Gabriele Piazza. 2023. "The role of large research infrastructures for regional innovation". In: Charitos, Panagiotis et al. *Big Science in the 21st Century*. Bristol: IOP Publishing. Chapter 14 (at press).
- 15) De Blasio, Guido, and Carlo Menon. 2012. "Local Effects of Manufacturing Employment Growth in Italy".
- 16) Denis, Kostin, Valeri Ayvazyan, Julien Branlard, Winfried Decking, Lutz Lilje, Mathieu Omet, Tobias Schnautz, Elmar Vogel, and Nicholas Walker. 'SRF Operation at XFEL: Lessons Learned After More Than One Year'. *Proceedings of the 10th Int. Particle Accelerator Conf. IPAC2019* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACOW-IPAC2019-MOYPLM2>.

- 17) Dotti, Nicola Francesco, André Spithoven, Ariane Wautelet, and Walter Ysebaert. 2021. "The 'Certain' Returns from Expenditures for 'Uncertain' Activities: A Local Multiplier Approach to Evaluate Regional R&I Policy." *European Planning Studies* 29 (2): 389–409. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2020.1758636>.
- 18) European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) (2020): Regional Trade Data for Europe. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] <http://data.europa.eu/89h/432cf8a7-fd5e-4816-a70c-633a7380c77c>
- 19) Feldman, Maryann. 2003. "The Locational Dynamics of the Us Biotech Industry: Knowledge Externalities and the Anchor Hypothesis." *Industry and Innovation* 10 (3): 311–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1366271032000141661>.
- 20) Florio, Massimo. 2019. *Investing in Science: Social Cost-Benefit Analysis of Research Infrastructures*. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11850.001.0001>.
- 21) Florio, Massimo, Francesco Giffoni, Anna Giunta, and Emanuela Sirtori. 2018. "Big Science, Learning, and Innovation: Evidence from CERN Procurement." *Industrial and Corporate Change* 27 (5): 915–36. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dty029>.
- 22) Florio, Massimo, and Emanuela Sirtori. 2016. "Social Benefits and Costs of Large Scale Research Infrastructures." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 112 (November): 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.11.024>.
- 23) Greco, Filomena. 2021. "Simic riveste d'acciaio i magneti per la fusione pulita in Francia." *Il Sole 24 ORE*, January. <https://www.ilsole24ore.com/art/simic-riveste-d-acciaio-magneti-la-fusione-pulita-francia-ADvNloCB>
- 24) Hanson, Andrew, and Shawn Rohlin. 2013. "Do Spatially Targeted Redevelopment Programs Spillover?" *Regional Science and Urban Economics* 43 (1): 86–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2012.05.002>.
- 25) Hazlett, Chad, and Yiqing Xu. 2018. "Trajectory Balancing: A General Reweighting Approach to Causal Inference With Time-Series Cross-Sectional Data." <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3214231>.
- 26) ISTAT. 2017. *Rapporto sulla Competitivita' dei settori produttivi*
- 27) ISTAT (2022). Registro statistico delle imprese attive. [Dataset] <http://dati.istat.it/?lang=en>
- 28) ISTAT. 2022. 2011 Census. [Dataset] <http://dati-censimentopopolazione.istat.it/Index.aspx?lang=en>
- 29) Jones, Benjamin. 2021. "Science and Innovation: The Under-fueled Engine of Prosperity.pdf." https://www.kellogg.northwestern.edu/faculty/jones-ben/htm/Science%20and%20Innovation%20_%20Underfueled%20Engine%20of%20Prosperity.pdf.
- 30) Kantor, Shawn, and Alexander Whalley. 2022. "Moonshot: Public R&D and Growth". <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hVWgALLLPXkZCVaHhz-rh7BASwPKzneU/view>
- 31) [Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze \(2021\), Imposta sul reddito delle persone fisiche](#). [Dataset] http://dati-censimentopopolazione.istat.it/Index.aspxhttps://www1.finanze.gov.it/finanze/analisi_stat/public/index.php?search_class%255b0%255d=cCOMUNE&opendat a=yes&privacy=ok
- 32) Moretti, Enrico. 2010. "Local Multipliers." *American Economic Review* 100 (2): 373–77. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.100.2.373>.
- 33) Neumann, Michael. 2014. "External effects of basic research infrastructure." MA thesis. <https://bib-pubdb1.desy.de/record/275796/files/Michael%20Neumann%20MA%20extended.pdf>
- 34) Noy, Chaim. 2008. "Sampling Knowledge: The Hermeneutics of Snowball Sampling in Qualitative Research." *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* 11 (4): 327–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570701401305>.
- 35) OECD (2021), Input-Output Tables.

- 36) Osman, Taner, and Tom Kemeny. 2022. "Local Job Multipliers Revisited." *Journal of Regional Science* 62 (1): 150–70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jors.12561>.
- 37) Peiniger, Michael, Michael Pekeler, and Hanspeter Vogel. 2012. "Industrialization of Superconducting RF Accelerator Technology." *Reviews of Accelerator Science and Technology* 05 (January): 265–83. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793626812300101>.
- 38) Porter, Michael E. 1998. "Clusters and the New Economics of Competition." *Harvard Business Review*, November. <https://hbr.org/1998/11/clusters-and-the-new-economics-of-competition>.
- 39) Quach, S., Fabian C, Kretzschmar L, Hütteneder M, Schmidle T, Tanson J, Schmidt M, and Deutschbauer S. 2021. "Evaluation of the market potential of HiPIMS and advanced coating technologies." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4551291>.
- 40) Singer, W., et al. 2016. "Production of Superconducting 1.3-GHz Cavities for the European x-Ray Free Electron Laser." *Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams* 19 (9): 092001. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.19.092001>.
- 41) Sirtori, Emanuela, Francesco Giffoni, Chiara Pancotti, Alessandra Caputo, Gelsomina Catalano, and Massimo Florio. 2019. "Impact of CERN Procurement Actions on Industry : 28 Illustrative Success Stories." <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2670056>.
- 42) The Economist. 2013. "Titans of Innovation." *The Economist*. <https://www.economist.com/business/2013/04/27/titans-of-innovation>.
- 43) The World Bank (2021). GDP deflator: linked series – Italy. [Dataset] <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.DEFL.ZS.AD?locations=IT>
- 44) Uyarra, Elvira, and Kieron Flanagan. 2010. "Understanding the Innovation Impacts of Public Procurement." *European Planning Studies* 18 (1): 123–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654310903343567>.
- 45) Uyarra, Elvira, Kieron Flanagan, Edurne Magro, and Jon Mikel Zabala-Iturriagoitia. 2017. "Anchoring the Innovation Impacts of Public Procurement to Place: The Role of Conversations." *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space* 35 (5): 828–48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399654417694620>.